

CLUTTER TUNING FOR BISTATIC CLUTTER CONTROL

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Abstract – In this paper, a radar modeling and simulation tool known as RLSTAP is used to model a bistatic clutter tuning scenario. The transmit system and the receive system "circle" the ground patch where the target lies in opposite senses so the Doppler shift due to the motion of the transmit (Tx) system is cancelled by an equal and opposite Doppler shift due to the motion of the receive (Rx) system. Key results are presented for this case, as well as for various imperfect clutter tuning cases and a monostatic case.

I. INTRODUCTION

Slow moving man-made objects of interest to military radar systems produce radar returns that can be masked by much stronger returns reflected from the surrounding terrain. This is especially true when the radar antenna is mounted in a sidelooking position with respect to the radar platform velocity vector. Doppler spread is the greatest when the radar antenna is sidelooking.

It is sometimes desirable to protect high value surveillance assets such as the Tx system in a "sanctuary" out of harm's way. Unfortunately, this sometimes places it well away from where the real action is, making it that much more difficult to perform the surveillance mission. Therefore, an adjunct receive radar system mounted aboard an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) may be employed to increase the effective range at which the overall system can perform surveillance. This overall system is known as a bistatic system, because of the two separate platform locations involved. Bistatic systems can help to overcome R^4 loss. There is also a possibility that the target RCS may be higher for the bistatic case.

A variety of techniques can be used to reduce the terrain clutter that a slow moving target return may be hidden in. Some of these fall into the realm of multi-dimensional radar signal processing. Key dimensions are space (angle), time ("slow time" i.e. one CPI), range ("fast time" i.e. the time between pulses in the same CPI), and polarization. Many people have focused heavily on processing in the space and time ("slow time") dimensions. This particular subset of multidimensional adaptive radar signal processing has become known as space time adaptive processing, or STAP.

Processing techniques such as STAP will not be needed in this paper. This is because large antenna electrical sizes, long CPI length, *a priori* knowledge of the target's position, and a

favorable scenario geometry make it possible for us to see a small, slow-moving target at a useful range without much difficulty using a single Rx channel.

In more general scenarios, however, sophisticated signal processing techniques would be required in order to mitigate bistatic clutter.

In [1], clutter tuning is mentioned as a possible technique for taking advantage of a favorable scenario geometry to help control bistatic clutter. The transmit and receive main beams must be fairly narrow for clutter tuning to work perfectly, and V_T/R_T must equal V_R/R_R , where V denotes velocity and R denotes slant range. In other words, the angular rotation rate of the transmit system about the ground patch must be equal and opposite to the angular rotation rate of the receive system about the ground patch. Imperfect clutter tuning results from the bistatic platforms not being properly oriented or the angular rotation rates of the transmit and receive systems about the ground patch not canceling each other out. Either one of these situations may exist in an operational setting.

In Section II, a nominal (close to ideal) clutter tuning scenario is laid out and nominal system parameters that make sense from a practical standpoint are collected for input into an RLSTAP workspace for generation of synthetic range-Doppler radar data. Here, "close to ideal" refers to the Tx & Rx platforms flying tangentially to target-centric circles instead of arcs of these circles. In Section III, Part A, synthetic range-Doppler radar data is generated for the nominal bistatic clutter tuning case. Then, the nominal clutter tuning scenario is altered to account for various imperfections such as heading misalignment of the Tx platform, and Rx platform speed deviations from ideal. A monostatic (both the Tx & Rx functions performed aboard the Tx platform) case is also run. The monostatic range-Doppler data provides a sort of benchmark against which the various bistatic range-Doppler plots can be compared. In Part B of Section III, minimum variance distortionless response (MVDR) plots for the nominal bistatic clutter tuning case and the monostatic case are shown because they show the structure of the terrain clutter across angle & Doppler for both cases. Section IV summarizes findings and results.

II. SCENARIO GEOMETRY AND SYSTEM PARAMETER SETUP

Refer to Fig. 1. A one square meter RCS point target is placed at 0.5 m above local ground level in rangeland in south central Florida. A bistatic scenario has been laid out with the target, Tx & Rx at the locations shown in Table I.

A bistatic radar system having the nominal parameters shown in Table II is now modeled. Parameters like Rx platform speed, Tx platform heading & Tx antenna electronic beamsteering angle will be altered for certain runs.

South central Florida has been chosen as the site for the target because of the flatness of the landscape and the absence of significant terrain undulations that might cause shadowing of the target at low grazing angles.

Scenario geometry calculations are performed offline to position the Tx & Rx systems relative to the target. Spherical trigonometry formulas [2] don't take the height of the Tx or Rx platforms into account, so occasionally simulation runs have to be redone with, say, yaw angles tweaked to point the Tx or Rx main beam at the target. Notional radar and platform parameters are used that make sense from a practicality standpoint but which are not representative of any fielded operational system.

Fig. 1. South Central Florida With The Ground Target Location Shown By A Small "+" Sign, With A Triangle Located Next To It.

TABLE I
TARGET & RADAR PLATFORM LOCATIONS

Tgt	26.5° N Lat, -80.999° E Lon, 6.5 m MSL (0.5 m AGL)
Tx Plat	23.89057621° N Lat, -81.76286271° E Lon, 10 km MSL
Rx Plat	25.63063182° N Lat, -80.74070892° E Lon, 10 km MSL

TABLE II
NOMINAL MODELING & SIMULATION PARAMETERS EMPLOYED

System/Scenario Parameters	Parameter Values
PRF	250 Hz (unambiguous in range)
Pulses/CPI Used in Processing	128 pulses
Frequency	10.0 GHz
Peak Power	400 kW
Transmit (Tx) Antenna	880 by 100 elements, lambda/2 spacing, uniform weighting horizontally, 50 dB Taylor weighting vertically, mechanically steered down 3.3032°, sidelooking to port
Receive (Rx) Antenna	256 by 60 elements, lambda/2 spacing, uniform weighting horizontally, 50 dB Taylor weighting vertically, 1 receive channel, mechanically steered down 6.1559°, sidelooking to starboard
Tx to Target Slant Range	~ 300 km
Rx to Target Slant Range	~ 100 km (bistatic runs)
Target RCS	1 square meter
Target Velocity	0.5 m/s due south
Target Height	0.5 meters above ground level in a patch of rangeland in south central Florida
System Losses	10 dB
Noise Figure	3 dB
Tx Platform Velocity	340 kts yaw angle = 104.65° wrt N.
Rx Platform Velocity	113.33 kts yaw angle = -105° wrt N.

Fig. 2. Diagram Illustrating The Scenario Geometry For The Nominal Case. "North" Denotes The Earth's North Pole. The Tx Is 15° Southwest Of The Target, And The Rx Is 15° Southeast Of The Target. This Figure Has Been Broken Into 2 Pieces For Ease Of Readability.

III. MODELING AND SIMULATION

A. Single Rx Channel Cases

After the geometry and notional system parameters are chosen for the nominal case, they are entered into an RLSTAP workspace that computes synthetic radar data and outputs the data into a Matlab-readable file for plotting.

RLSTAP culls insignificant terrain scatterers from the clutter computation for a speed increase. This leaves the terrain shown in Fig. 3. Note the target symbol superimposed. Also note the antenna pattern-like shape of the patches of remaining terrain. This is expected, since the Tx & Rx antenna gains impinging on the Earth's surface have a profound effect on determining which terrain scatterers will contribute significantly to the clutter return.

Fig. 3. Terrain After Insignificant Clutter Scatterers Are Culled. The Target Position Is Denoted By The Small “+” Sign, With A Triangle Located Next To It.

Radar data is generated for a single Rx channel only (the entire Rx aperture is connected to one channel). The range-Doppler data plane in the vicinity of the main beam region is shown in Fig. 4, and again in Fig. 5, which focuses more closely on the region around the target return.

Note the shape of the clutter return as a function of bistatic range. Note that it crosses zero Doppler at about the target's range. This is due to the fact that the Tx & Rx platforms are each flying tangentially to circles about the terrain patch lying in the Tx + Rx main beam, so main beam clutter has zero radial velocity with respect to the Tx and Rx. The Tx & Rx platforms are both at 10 km above mean sea level (MSL). The Tx platform is flying southeast and has the ground patch

on its left, and the Rx system is flying southwest and has the ground patch on its right. If the Tx & Rx slant ranges to the target were made equal, the Tx & Rx aircraft would crash into each other. Since the Tx aircraft is about 300 km from the target, and the Rx aircraft is about 100 km from the target, this will not happen. In order to maintain an equal and opposite angular rotation rate about the main beam ground patch, the Tx platform speed must be about three times the Rx platform speed. This relationship agrees well with the ratio of expected cruising speeds for platforms of the type envisioned for use as Tx and Rx platforms (the Tx platform would probably be sized much like a commercial airliner, while the Rx platform, a UAV, would probably be much smaller, lighter and slower).

Fig. 4. Beta = 30 Degrees, Zoomed-Out Range-Doppler Plot, No Electronic Beamsteering.

Fig. 5. Beta = 30 Degrees, No Electronic Beamsteering.

“Beta = 30°” appearing in the plot titles refers to the angle on the earth's surface from the Tx nadir point to the target (at the vertex of the triangle) to the Rx nadir point. Other cases not shown in this paper have been run with beta equal to 40° and 50°. These runs confirmed that clutter tuning is causing

the main beam clutter (at the peak of both the Tx & Rx main beams) to lie at zero Doppler. In other words, the nominal case is not just a happy coincidence that can not be replicated at other flight paths tangential to target-centric circles about the ground patch.

Next, cases are simulated where the Tx platform isn't truly aligned to travel tangentially to a target-centric circle, but instead has a more southerly component to its heading & velocity vectors, here assumed to be the same. To put the Tx main beam on the target, the Tx antenna has to electronically steer away from the antenna normal (sidelooking in azimuth) toward the rear of the Tx platform by 20° or 30° off the Tx array normal. The Rx platform again flies the tangential course that it flew in the nominal case, with no electronic beamsteering necessary.

Results are shown in Figs. 6 & 7. The target return can clearly be seen, but the terrain clutter at the peak of the Tx & Rx main beams (around the target range) is no longer close to zero Doppler. Instead, it is gradually being slid away from the zero as the Tx platform heading and velocity depart from the tangential course considered in the nominal case. This necessitates greater amounts of electronic beamsteering to place the Tx main beam peak on the target. Obviously, in extreme cases, the Tx platform can be so severely misaligned with respect to the ideal tangential course that electronic beamsteering is no longer practical.

Fig. 6. Beta = 30 Degrees, Tx Antenna Electronically Beamsteered 20 Degrees To Compensate For Heading Misalignment.

Next, the effect of non-equal and opposite angular rotation rates about the main beam terrain is studied (see Figs. 8 & 9). This time we use the Rx platform for our scenario alterations. The Rx platform speed is first made equal to half the nominal speed, then to twice the nominal speed. We notice that the terrain clutter becomes more spread out in wispy tendrils and is therefore much less tractable, potentially giving us greater difficulty in separating the terrain clutter from the target return. If the target were truly at the main beam peak for both

the (sidelooking) Tx and Rx antennas, it shouldn't move in Doppler at all as a function of Tx and Rx platform velocity. However, the target is not quite at the peak of the Rx main beam, causing the slight Doppler shifting of the target between Figs. 8 & 9 as Rx platform speed is adjusted.

Fig. 7. Beta = 30 Degrees, Tx Antenna Electronically Beamsteered 30 Degrees To Compensate For Heading Misalignment.

Finally, a monostatic case is run where it is assumed that there is no UAV Rx system available or in position, and we are forced to do monostatic surveillance from aboard the Tx platform. Again, it is assumed that only a single Rx channel is used (i.e. the entire aperture feeds into a single Rx channel). The results are shown in Fig. 10. The target return shows up quite clearly. Of course, if the Tx system hadn't been flying tangentially to the target-centric circle at a position where the target's radial velocity toward the Tx system was close to its total velocity, the target wouldn't stand out so clearly.

Fig. 8. Beta = 30 Degrees, Rx Platform Moving Half As Fast As It Should Be If It Is To Meet The Bistatic Clutter Tuning Velocity/Slant Range Constraint.

No conventional or adaptive processing has been performed in generating the bistatic or monostatic range-Doppler plots in this paper. The entire aperture on receive is

connected to a single Rx channel. In more general cases, where advantages such as electrically large antennas, *a priori* target location knowledge, long CPIs and favorable scenario geometries are not available, multiple Rx channels and sophisticated signal processing techniques would be required.

Fig. 9. Beta = 30 Degrees, Rx Platform Moving Twice As Fast As It Should Be If It Is To Meet The Bistatic Clutter Tuning Velocity/Slant Range Constraint.

Figs. 11 & 12 are included for the sake of completeness. Fig. 11 shows the terrain scatterers whose clutter returns are included by RLSTAP in the monostatic synthetic data computation, because their clutter returns are significant enough due to Tx & Rx antenna gain, range, & clutter backscattering coefficient. The "Normalized Scatter" term in Fig. 12 refers to terrain patch dependent factors (cell area * sigma zero / R⁴) that occur in the radar range equation.

The plots in Figs. 11 & 12 resemble the Tx main beam squared impinging on the ground. This is because the Tx antenna is also used on Rx for the monostatic case modeled here.

Fig. 10. Monostatic Case, With Both The Transmit And Receive Functions Being Performed By The Antenna Aboard The Transmit Platform.

Fig. 11. Terrain Map For The Monostatic Case. The Target Position Is Denoted By The Small "+" Sign, With A Triangle Located Next To It.

Fig. 12. Transmit Gain * Receive Gain * Normalized Scatter For The Monostatic Case. The Target Position Is Denoted By The Small "+" Sign, With A Triangle Located Next To It.

B. Multiple Rx Channel Cases – MVDR Plots

In more general scenarios, multiple Rx channels are required for both bistatic and monostatic systems in order to obtain the angular resolution necessary when attempting to detect challenging targets in a severe interference environment. In-depth investigation of multi-channel processing is beyond the scope of this paper. However, a minimum variance distortionless response (MVDR) plot is included here for both the nominal bistatic clutter tuning

scenario as well as for the monostatic scenario. These plots (Figs. 13 & 14) illustrate the terrain clutter's structure across angle and Doppler. These have been generated by breaking the Rx aperture up into 16 horizontal, non-overlapping subapertures with a Rx channel behind each subaperture to achieve a certain amount of angular resolution, and using a subset of the pulses in the CPI (16 out of 128) for Doppler resolution. Much finer Doppler resolution could be had by using more of the available pulse returns in generating the MVDR spectra, but this has not been done. It would require a lot more sample support than could reasonably be provided in a practical case from range bins to either side of the one in which the target lies. Note that the antenna aboard the Tx platform is used on Rx as well as on Tx in the monostatic case, so the Tx antenna must also be broken into 16 non-overlapping subapertures, with a Rx channel behind each subaperture.

Fig. 13. MVDR Plot For The Bistatic Clutter Tuning Case.

Fig. 14. MVDR Plot For The Monostatic (Aboard Tx Platform) Case.

IV. SUMMARY

As stated previously, the radar antennas used here are electrically large, eliminating much of the terrain clutter that would otherwise have appeared. The CPI is so long that the target, though slow-moving, is placed far enough away from the main beam clutter that it can be clearly seen.

There are simplifying bistatic geometries that make a radar signal processor's job a lot easier, and it makes sense to take advantage of these geometries when they present themselves. In more general cases, however, adaptive processing is required.

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REFERENCES

- [1] N. J. Willis, *Bistatic Radar*, Artech House, 1991, pp. 238-244.
- [2] W. H. Beyer, *Standard Mathematical Tables, 26th Edition*, CRC Press, 1984, pp. 145-148.